

Effects of Sequential Teaching Methods on Retention in Biology among Senior Secondary School Students in Niger State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined Effects of Sequential Teaching Methods on Retention in Biology among Senior Secondary School Students in Niger State, Nigeria. Quasi-experimental research design specifically, pre-test, post-test and post-post-test control group design was adopted for the study. Two research questions and corresponding null hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study consists of 165,034 (85,034 Male and 80,000 female) government senior secondary school class two (SSII) students during the 2022/2023 academic session in Niger State. 100 (51 Male and 49 Female) students constitute the sample size of the study using multi-stage sampling technique. The instruments for data collection were 30-item Biology Retention Test (BRT) validated by experts. Reliability coefficient of 0.85 was obtained using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient reliability test. Descriptive statistics were used to answer the two research questions, while ANCOVA was used to test null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that there was significant difference in students' retention in Biology between those exposed to sequential teaching methods and their counterparts taught with conventional method. Base on the findings of the study, it was further concluded that sequential teaching methods has positive effect on students' retention and is gender friendly. Hence, it was recommended that regular workshops, seminars and conferences should be held for teachers to make them familiar with the knowledge of sequential teaching methods and should be encouraged to explore the method frequently during teaching and learning process.

Keyword: Sequential teaching methods, biology, students, gender and retention

Introduction

Biology is the study of living organisms, their origins, anatomy, morphology, physiology, behavior and distribution. It studies life processes of a group or category of living organisms. A lot of reasons are borne in mind while studying Biology. These include among others, the understanding of self and the environment surrounding us, appreciation of nature as well as pollution control. Thus, Biology and its study are necessary not only for students but the whole of human populace. Of all the science subjects, Biology is the only descriptive science which is very much linked to human life unlike Chemistry and Physics which are quantitative in nature. Biology is one of the core science subjects that senior secondary school students offer in Nigerian secondary schools, it was introduced to students at this level as a preparatory ground for human development, where career abilities are groomed, potentials and talents are discovered and energized (FGN, 2013). It is also a prerequisite for higher learning in a number of sciences related professional courses like medicine, zoology, botany, biochemistry and microbiology. Biology is very wide with many branches such as genetics, ecology, morphology, evolution and the more advanced cell biology among others.

Science has a unique nature and it is an organized body of knowledge in form of concepts, laws, theories and generalizations. Ugbong (2016) defined science as a study of nature and natural phenomena in order to discover their principles and laws. Science enhances national development and also exposes an individual to recent ideas through reasoning and mental efforts (Orji & Anaduaka, 2010). All nations in the world including Nigeria are striving hard to improve or develop technologically and scientifically. This could be achieved through laying a solid foundation in science and technology studies. Science as school subjects comprises of Physics, Chemistry, Mathematics, Agriculture and Biology. Science Education is defined as the study of the connection between science as a discipline and the application of educational principles to comprehend science teaching and learning in the classroom (Dabah, 2016). Therefore, science education acquaints students with certain basic knowledge, skills and attitudes needed for future work in science and science-related fields. The impact of science education on national development could be felt in several ways; as it

provides humanity with knowledge about the environment, attitudes and values for social living, knowledge and skills to explore and transform resources, change in quality of life and improvement in economy (Udofia, 2010)

There are many factors that have been identified by researchers as being responsible for the decline and poor retention of students in Biology; some of these include; lack of instructional materials, lack of qualified teachers, lack of educational facilities like laboratories, overloaded syllabuses, laziness, poor attitude and lack of interest on the part of the students, large class size, family/home background of the students (Osuafor & Okonkwo, 2013; Sadi & Haruna, 2020)). Based on this premise, sequential usage of three teaching methods was applied: demonstration, discussion and conventional (talk-chalk) in teaching Biology content in a sequence of use in order to ascertain their effects on students' retention. Sequence is an act of putting events, ideas, and objects in a logical order (Frank, 2013). Sequential teaching method is an instructional method that engages students to learn a particular topic in logical order of display or is a process of imparting knowledge to learners using different instructional methods in logical order. It provides a concrete basis for conceptual thinking (promoting critical thinking skills).

Demonstration method involves the use of instructional materials to show learners how something is done in order to enable them acquire skills necessary for performing the given task. The method is mostly used in showing the students correct use of certain science equipment. Demonstration can be carried out as: teacher centred approach, quasi student centred approach or student centred approach. The method encourages students' participation which is necessary for teaching and learning in the classroom. It is a strategy that focuses on achieving psychomotor and cognitive objectives (Azubuike & Mumuni, 2018). Discussion method involves a group of people in a class who come together to exchange ideas, facts, opinions and expressions orally about a topic of mutual concern and interest under a guide. In a discussion class, the students talk to each other about the concept or problem until there is an agreeable understanding to it mentally. This method encourages children to be independent of teacher and discover knowledge and also see relationship on their own. The discussion method involves intelligent exchange of views, ideas and opinions on a topic, which covers a wide range of classroom activities and interactions or it involves written and oral expression of different points of view in a given situation (Cashin, 2011).

The lecture method (talk-chalk) is concerned with the teacher being the controller of the learning environment. It does not encourage deeper students' involvement as they are passive recipient of information already acquired by the teacher. Also, it does not facilitate the development of reasoning skills and processes in the students. These among other reasons had not enhanced learning in students and thus had led to poor retention of Biology concepts among students in secondary schools (Merriam & Grace, 2011). Retention involves the ability to recall the content that has been taught within a specific period of time. It is the ability exhibited by learner to demonstrate what he/she has learnt and has been able to demonstrate his/her cognitive skills in the subject learnt (Emmanuel, Ogbaba & Ahmed, 2014). Also retention means the ability to store information which can be easily recalled from the short term memory and long term memory (Alake, 2015). Fakotun & Eniayeju (2014) wrote that retention can be measured through verbal recall of learnt materials that is, the cognitive ability of learners. Retention occurs when experience are coded in the memory. There are many factors that may affect retention of Biology concepts, which are: Age, as one grows older the cells become weaker and weaker. The intervening variable influencing students' retention in Biology at SSCE is gender. Gender is a social construct that differentiate male from female based on physical features. Many researchers (Apochi, 2017, Nneka, 2015; Abdul-Raheem, 2012 & Okoro, 2011) have shown gender to be of significant influence in an investigation of this nature, hence the inclusion of gender as an intervening variable in this study. Based on this background therefore, the present study examined the effects of sequential teaching methods (STM) on retention in Biology among senior secondary school students.

The teaching of science particularly Biology should be consistent with the nature of science which lays greater emphasis on engaging students in inquiry activities as the use of one-size-fits-all curriculum no longer meets the needs of majority of learners. Education is an indispensable instrument for the development of any nation and teachers are the implementers of the educational programme and theories into practice. Hence, due to the usefulness of biology in nearly all fields of human endeavor, the poor retention of students biting hard at senior secondary schools' level is of significant concern to stakeholders in education. To buttressed this fact, it is observed by the Chief Examiners' Report of West African Examination Council (WAEC 2017-2023) that, the problem affecting poor achievement in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination is attributed to poor teaching delivery or teacher's method of presenting the content of the curriculum to learners amongst others, the results in 2017 showed that, one million, five hundred and fifty-nine thousand, one hundred and sixty-two (1,559,162) candidates sat for final examinations, 79.77% (1,243,772) have credits in five subjects including English Language and Mathematics while 20.23% failed. But it further disclosed that there was declined in 2018, 2019 and 2020 with 42.64%, 35.82% and 34.76% failures respectively as shown in table below:

Table 1: Chief Examiners' Report of West African Examination Council (WAEC 2017-2023)

Year	No of candidates that sat for examinations	Number that passed	% that passed	Number that failed	% that failed
2017	1,559,162	1,243,772	79.77%	315,390	20.23%
2018	1,099,902	1,077,749	57.35%	2,153	42.64%
2019	1,600,000	1,020,519	64.18%	579,481	35.82%
2020	1,538,445	1,003,668	65.24%	534,777	34.76%
2021	1,560,261	1,398,370	89.62%	161,891	10.38%
2022	1,601,047	1,222,505	76.36%	378,542	23.64%
2023	1,613,733	1,287,920	79.81%	325,813	20.19%

Furthermore, Nwagbo (2011), also assert that the persistent negative retention of students in Biology and other related science subjects is attributed to inappropriate teaching method adopted by the teachers. In addition, Biology teachers use talk-chalk/lecture method to teach the subject, which does not in any way provide sequence of learning experience that is, the talk-chalk/lecture method is imperfect because it involves verbal presentation of pre-planned lesson to the students which requires little or no instructional aid and so does not promote students' higher level of thinking (Dajal & Mohammed, 2019).

Furthermore, the persistent use of these methods makes students passive rather than active learners and does not promote insightful learning and long-term retention of some abstract concepts in biology (Umar, 2011). Therefore, considering the importance of biology in all round development there is need for change in strategy/method in teaching so as to enable students in senior secondary schools to acquire adequate knowledge and skills in science. In the same vein, researchers in science education especially Biology have always been searching for better teaching method that will enhance better students' retention and promote their attitude so that they perform well in Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations. In order to improve on the teaching and learning of Biology by exploring an innovative learner-centred method, it's therefore necessary to investigate sequential teaching methods on students' retention.

Objectives of the study

1. Examine the mean retention scores of students taught Biology with sequential teaching methods and those taught with conventional method;
2. Find out the mean retention scores of male and female students taught Biology with sequential teaching methods.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide this study:

1. What is the mean retention scores of students taught Biology using sequential teaching methods and those exposed to Lecture teaching method in Government secondary schools in Niger State?
2. What is the mean retention scores of male and female students taught Biology using sequential teaching methods in Government secondary schools in Niger State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at significant level of 0.05.

1. There is no significant difference in mean retention scores of students taught Biology using sequential teaching methods and those exposed to Lecture teaching method in Government secondary schools in Niger State
2. There is no significant difference between mean retention scores of male and female students taught Biology using sequential teaching methods in Government secondary schools in Niger State.

Methodology

The research design for this study was quasi-experimental research design specifically, pre-test and post-test non equivalent control group. Being an experimental study, the samples for the studies were grouped into experimental and control groups. The experimental group was taught biology concepts (Ecological Management: Association, Tolerance, Adaptation, Pollution, Nutrient Cycling in nature, Basic Ecological Concepts, Population Studies and Conservation of Natural Resources) using sequential teaching methods while the control group was taught the same biology concepts (Ecological Management: Association, Tolerance, Adaptation, Pollution, Nutrient Cycling in nature, Basic Ecological Concepts, Population Studies and Conservation of Natural Resources) using conventional talk-chalk method. Intact classes were used in order to avoid distortion on the normal class settings using the school timetables. The design is presented symbolically in Table 1.

Table 2: Representation of Research Design

Group	Pre-test	Treatment	Post-post test	Post-post test
Experiment	O_1	X_1	O_2	O_3
Control	O_1	X_1	O_2	O_3

The population of the study consists of 165,034 (85,034 Male and 80,000 female) government senior secondary school class two (SSII) students during the 2022/2023 academic session in Niger State. 100 (51 Male and 49 Female) students constitutes the sample size of the study using multi-stage sampling technique. At first stage, simple random sampling was used to select a Local Government Area from the twenty-five (25) Local Government Areas in Niger state. The reason for the choice of simple random sampling technique is to give each Local Government Area equal chance of being selected in the study. At the second stage, two co-educational secondary schools were selected using simple random sampling technique. The choice of co-education schools was because gender is one of the variables in the study. At the third stage of sampling, one intact class of Biology students in SSII from the two sampled schools was selected randomly (hat-draw method) and the two classes were assigned experimental group and control group.

The instruments used for data collection in this study Biology Retention Test (BRT) was used for test of retention. It consisted of two sections: Section A and Section B. Section A entails the general information of the students while Section B entails the Biology Retention Test questions. The BRT comprised of thirty (30) items multiple choice objective test questions with four (4) options lettered A, B, C and D. The question numbers were administered as post-post-test to both experimental and control groups and the test was conducted 30 days of post-test in order to avoid retention error and help the researcher investigate the effect of sequential teaching methods on students' retention in Biology. The test items were based on concepts in ecological management: association, tolerance, adaptation, pollution, nutrients cycling in nature, basic ecological concepts, population studies and conservation of natural resources adopted from past West African Examination Council (WAEC, 2019-2023 standardized questions). The researcher prepared a table of specification (Test blue print) to guide the test development, in accordance to the senior secondary curriculum.

The researcher prepared two sets of lesson plans for teaching both experimental and control groups for each topic that was taught; each unit contained eight lessons that lasted for eight weeks. One set of lesson plan was prepared using sequential teaching methods while the other set was prepared based on conventional method. The Biology Retention Test (BRT) was subjected to scrutiny by four experts in the subject area and was content validated using table of specification and face validation by experts in the Department of Science and Environmental Education, University of Abuja; and two Biology teachers from sampled senior secondary schools in Tafa LGA, Niger state. The comments and recommendations of the experts had helped in selection and modification of the test items for the study. After the validation, the BRT items were subjected to Split half reliability test. A split half method was used to compute the reliability of the Biology Retention Test. It was administered once and the scores were divided into two to calculate the reliability of the instrument.

A method of estimating reliability involved twenty-five (25) senior secondary II Biology students (15 male and 10 female). Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) was used to calculate the internal consistency of the BRT. This method of estimating the internal consistency reliability of an instrument is appropriate for dichotomously scored items such as BRT which is a multiple-choice objective test with right and wrong answers and is easier to use. The outcome of the reliability estimate warranted modifications in the test item (BRT). The reliability coefficient of the instrument gave $r = 0.85$. Thus, BRT was considered reliable. The treatment lasted for a period of eight weeks of treatment, BRT instrument was administered as pre-test for both experimental and control groups; after the first week, the researcher went round the sampled schools and taught students personally for eight (8) weeks during their lesson period using the prepared lesson plans and notes was given. The researcher administered the BRT post post-test. The data collected were analyzed accordingly. The scores obtained were analyzed using descriptive statistics frequent counts, mean and standard deviations for the research questions while the hypotheses were using ANCOVA at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the mean retention scores of students taught Biology using sequential teaching methods and those exposed to Lecture teaching method in Government secondary schools in Niger State?

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Table 2: Mean and standard deviation showing retention scores of students taught Biology using sequential teaching methods and lecture teaching method

Treatment Groups	N	Pre-test X Sd.	Post-test X Sd.	Mean Difference
Sequential Teaching Methods (Experimental)	51	15.741.00	64.9630.23	49.2
Lecture Teaching Method (Control)	49	15.093.55	41.5441.38	26.450
Total	100			

Source: 2023 Field work data statistics

In Table 2, the mean scores of the students in the sequential teaching methods (experimental group) on pre-test and post-test are 15.74 and 64.96 respectively. These results give a post-test - pre-test mean difference of 49.22; while those of the students in conventional method (control group) are 15.09 and 41.54 respectively, giving a post-test - pretest mean difference of 23.42. The gains in scores show that the students in the experimental group taught sequential teaching method (23.42) performed better than their counterparts in conventional method (0.65). Considering the research question one - what are the mean retention scores of students taught Biology with sequential teaching methods and those taught with conventional method? - The observations indicate that students taught using sequential teaching method retained better than those taught with the conventional teacher-centered method.

Research Question 2

What is the mean retention scores of male and female students taught Biology using sequential teaching methods in Government Secondary schools in Niger State?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation showing retention scores of male and female Students taught Biology using sequential teaching methods

Gender	N	Pre-test	Post-test	Mean Difference
		X Sd.	X Sd.	
Male	27	13.541.26	17.960.62	4.425
Female	24	13.669.56	17.920.00	4.261
Total	51			

Source : 2023 Field work data statistics

Table 3 the mean scores of the male students in the sequential teaching methods (experimental group) on pre-test and post-test are 13.54 and 17.96 respectively. These results give a post-test - pre-test mean difference of 4.43; while female students also taught the same instructional strategy are 13.67 and 17.92 respectively, giving a post-test - pretest mean difference of 4.26. The mean difference of 0.164 is an indication that both gender retained equally. A comparison of these retentions indicates that both male and female in sequential teaching methods had similar knowledge. These observations answered the question two - what are the mean retention cores of male and female students taught Biology with sequential teaching methods?

Hypotheses Testing

H₀₁:

There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of students taught Biology using sequential teaching methods and those exposed to Lecture teaching method in Government secondary schools in Niger State.

Table 4: Summary of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Biology Students taught using Sequential Teaching Methods and Lecture Teaching Method

Source of Variation	Type III Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F.cal	Sig.	Decision at p<.05
Corrected Model	7681.545 ^a	3	4230.512	81.634	.000	S
Intercept	4762.004	1	4762.006	114.240	.000	S
Covariate Pre-test	174.15	1	174.15	6.431	.063	Ns

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Methods	8762.202	1	4286.807	144.341	.000	s
Error	4173.710	141				
Total	119631.000	134				
Corrected Total	9766.276	130				

a. R Squared = .787 (Adjusted R Squared = .781)

Table 4, reading on the row Methods revealed that Mean Square = 8762.202, $F = 144.341$, $df = 1$ and $Sig. = .000 = p$. Since $p < 0.05$, the noted difference between retention scores of students taught using sequential teaching methods and conventional method is significant. So, the null hypothesis was rejected with the conclusion that there is a significant difference between the mean retention scores of the students taught using sequential teaching methods and those taught Biology with conventional method.

H₀₂:

There is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of male and female students taught Biology using sequential teaching methods in Government secondary schools in Niger State.

Table 5: Summary of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Male and Female Students taught Biology using Sequential Teaching Methods

Source of Variation	Type III Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F_{cal}	Sig.	Decision at $p < .05$
Corrected Model	56.355 ^a	2	23.436	.482	.342	Ns
Intercept	4163.420	1	4163.420	62.422	.000	S
Covariate Pre-test	62.023	1	62.023	2.003	.344	Ns
Sex	5.842	1	5.842	.163	.602	ns
Error	7122.411	70				
Total	6643.001	67				
Corrected Total	4071.374	68				

a. R Squared = .788 (Adjusted R Squared = .782)

Table 5, reading on the row heading Sex, revealed that Mean Square = 5.842, $F = .163$, $df = 1$ and $Sig. = .602 = p$. Since $p > 0.05$, the note in the difference of students taught using sequential teaching methods between male and female students is not significant. So, the null hypothesis was not rejected with the conclusion that there is no significant difference between the retention scores of male and female students taught Biology using sequential teaching methods.

Discussion of Findings

The first findings revealed that students taught Biology using sequential teaching methods retained significantly better than those taught using conventional method. This finding is in agreement with Snezana, Liljana & Milena (2011) and Namasaka, Mondoh & Chrulukovian, (2017) who found significant differences in favour of experimental group meaning the method gives retention of knowledge more than the oratory conventional method predominantly used in most places worldwide. Similarly, Ajaja (2013), Abdulhamid (2013) and Owolabi & Oginni (2013) showed that learning styles increases motivation, attracts attention and retention among learners. However, the results of these findings negate that of Amosa, Akawo, Gana & Ugovwa (2014), who asserted that there was no significant difference in the mean scores retention of students.

The second findings revealed that male and female students taught biology using sequential teaching methods did not differ significantly in their mean retention scores. This finding agreed with Oludipe (2012), who underscores sequential teaching methods as gender friendly. In a similar study by Gongden & Delmang (2016) recorded no significant difference in male and female students in experimental group. However, this contradict the findings of Duyilemi & Bolajoko (2014), Okeke (2011) which revealed that male students' retention was significantly higher than that of their female counterpart exposed to three (3) interaction patterns (cooperative, competitive and individualistic patterns of learning); This is so because the learner centered method promote low retention ability due to lack of active engagement or participation of some female students learning culture.

Conclusion

This article examined the Effects of Sequential Teaching Methods on Retention in Biology among Senior Secondary School Students in Niger State. The result revealed that STM significantly enhanced retention in Biology. That is, when STM is used to teach Biology, student's retention magnifies. Also, gender has no significant effect on students' retention. This study finally concluded that the use of sequential teaching methods was resourceful, innovative and would be a good asset to Biology teachers and students. The result revealed that students taught STM had drastic positive effect on students' retention in Biology. Also, it enhanced cooperate learning than those taught using lecture teaching method. Gender has no significant effect on students' retention. This study finally concluded that the use of sequential teaching methods was resourceful, innovative and would be a good asset to Biology teachers and students.

Based on the finding of the study, sequential teaching methods enhance student's retention due to its stimulation of attention or curiosity in the students by making them desirous to learn and know Biology. This finding makes the researcher to conclude that sequential teaching methods are elegant to students' retention and gender friendly.

Recommendations

Based on the findings in this study the following recommendations were made:

1. Teacher education institutions are encouraged to include sequential teaching methods in their Biology curriculum for training and retraining in workshops, seminars,
2. Biology teachers in schools should be encouraged to use sequential teaching methods in teaching other concepts.
3. Curriculum developers when developing curriculum, should embrace innovative teaching strategies like STM to enhance acquisition of critical thinking, problem solving and achievement skills for both genders.

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